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The Indian-American Immigrant: The Hyphenated Alien - A Study of Sunil Gangopadhyay's Novel *Purbo-Paschim* (Vol II)

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Abstract

This paper examines the phenomenon of Indian-American diasporic identity formation, as represented in Bengali novelist Sunil Gangopadhyay's Bengali novel Purbo-Paschim. Responses to the experience of migration to America from India have found varied portrayals in the works of Indian-American writers. However, a Calcutta based Bengali writer's delving into this issue is a rarity. Critical conversations around Gangopadhyay's works also have not probed his representation of this aspect. This study focuses on Gangopadhyay's depiction of the Indian-American diasporic experience in Purbo-Paschim through the character of Atin, and Atin's eventual epitomization of the lack of a stable identity of the diasporic subject.

Keywords: diaspora, Indian-American, hyphenated identity, world literature, migration.

1 Introduction

This paper examines the experience of cross-cultural migration from India to America and its associated process of Indian-American diasporic identity formation, as represented in the second volume of Bengali novelist Sunil Gangopadhyay's Bengali novel *Purbo-Paschim* (East-West). Responses to the experience of migration to America from India have found variedly nuanced portrayals in the works of Indian-American writers like Jhumpa Lahiri, Bharati Mukherjee, and Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni. However, a Calcutta based Bengali writer like Sunil Gangopadhyay's delving into this issue in a Bengali novel is an interesting rarity. Writer and poet Sunil Gangopadhyay¹ was one of the stalwarts of modern Bengali literature; he as, Suhrid Chattopadhyay writes, "for [...] four decades [...] strode like a colossus the cultural domain of Bengal on both sides of the international border, impacting various aspects of the arts - poetry, novel, short story, children's fiction, drama, travelogue" (Chattopadhyay 2012). Sunil Gangopadhyay had stayed in the United States of America in 1963-64 on a scholarship to attend the Iowa Writers' Workshop. As he states in his autobiography *Ardhek Jibon [Half a Life]*, he was faced with the "serious crisis" (Gangopadhyay 2002: 262) of deciding between staying in the USA which offered the prospect of a well-paid job as a librarian at the Iowa University, and returning to Calcutta with economic uncertainty as well as the possibility of never regaining his place amidst his circle of friends. Although the job at the Iowa University library would have provided him the opportunity to pursue further studies as well as engage in writing, Gangopadhyay mentions linguistic alienation in America and his need to be in a Bengali speaking ethos to write in Bengali, as the deciding factor for his choice of returning to Calcutta (Gangopadhyay 2002: 262-267). This life event may have prompted Sunil Gangopadhyay to explore the question of diasporic subject position through his character Atin Majumder in *Purbo-Paschim Vol II*.

2 Literary Analysis

Sunil Gangopadhyay presents a nuanced and complex trajectory of the immigrant experience, marked by distinct, layered, and even contradictory phases. In his first phase as an immigrant in America, a young Atin in his early twenties perceives migration to America as a process of alienation and exile. What he can receive in the new world is completely overshadowed by the pains of what has been lost by leaving home. For him, immigration to America in this phase is a continuous struggle for survival in an alien universe. His sense of dislocation from his own space and alienation in the new space is accentuated by his stubborn refusal to adapt to life in America. Instead of acknowledging the positives that America brings to him, Atin is highly sceptical of his new world as is reflected in his pervasive criticism of American practices. Gangopadhyay highlights this through several instances in the text. For instance, in his initial days in New York, Atin works in a job of loading and unloading goods in a supermarket, and defiantly responds to queries about his occupation as “I am a coolie” (Gangopadhyay 1989: 102)⁵; when told by Bengali expatriate acquaintances that it is commonplace for youngsters to work in such jobs in America as Americans believe in dignity of labour, he vehemently responds - “what is dignity of labour; in this country one cannot survive even a day without money, and hence, people are compelled to take up such jobs. There is absolutely no dignity of labour in being educated and working as a coolie or a servant” (Gangopadhyay 1989: 102).

Atin perceives his initial years in America as a painful exile from what is his own. According to Edward Said, exile is “solitude outside the group; the deprivations felt at not being with others” (Said 2000: 177). For Atin living in America is, however, not being in exile only psychologically or socially; it is in fact literal, a denouement of political circumstances. Atin had been compelled to immigrate to America to escape punishment for the criminal offence of murder he had committed as a Naxalite. Michael Gillespie states, “[...] the reality at the heart of the matter is that exile is thrust upon individuals who can no longer sustain themselves in the land that they have considered their homes” (Gillespie 2015: 5). According to Bill Ashcroft et al., the word exile indicates, “the state of being sent to another country that is not your own, especially for political reasons, or as a punishment” (Ashcroft et al. 1998: 86). Further, the merciless massacre of the Naxalites back home nullifies Atin’s possibilities of returning to Calcutta. Depicting the horrifying situation of the Naxalites in the early 1970s, Jawhar Sircar writes:

S.S. Ray’s government had decided to use some army regiments to assist civil police in “exterminating the Naxalite menace”. As General JFR Jacob of the Eastern Command confessed later on, sections of the army joined hands with the local police to hunt down Naxalites — in what was branded as Operation Steeple Chase [...] the Naxalites were then shot in cold blood, often tied to lampposts, or at their very own doorsteps. Some were arrested and taken in police vans and many never seen ever again. Stories were rife of how these police vans stopped in the middle of nowhere, late in the night. The police opened the doors of the vans, freed the arrested Naxalites and told them to run away. But as soon as they did so, they were shot dead in the back. The official story was that they were escaping from police custody.

(Sircar 2021)

In the novel, Atin’s friend in New York, Siddhartha, corroborates such persecution of the Naxalites. He tells Atin:

I read in the tabloid *India Abroad* that Siddhartha Ray's government has adopted a new tactic. They are not sending the Naxalites to the court. The Naxalites are being taken in police vans to the Maidan, where they are being released and told to run away. The moment they start running away, they are shot dead from behind. This process has been termed as an encounter [...] You are lucky to have escaped from the country at the right time; if you were in jail now, you would not have survived.

(Gangopadhyay 1989: 24)

Atin is thus subjected to a state of two-fold exile—psychological due to his difficulty and resistance to relate to the new milieu of America, as well as literal, caused by the political circumstances of his homeland.

The perception of exile can be equated with the sense of alienation. This state of double exile and alienation is intensified in Atin's case both due to his own response of resisting adaptation to his new world, and the circumstances specific to him as an escaped Naxalite. Often for immigrants the only source of solace in an alien land becomes their circle of immigrant friends who share the same origin. Jhumpa Lahiri, in her novel *The Namesake*, presents such an immigrant situation:

They all come from Calcutta, and for this reason alone they are friends [...] The families drop by one another's home unexpected on Sunday afternoons. They drink tea with sugar and evaporated milk and eat shrimp cutlets fried in saucepans. They sit in circles on the floor, singing songs by Nazrul and Tagore [...] They argue riotously over the films of Ritwik Ghatak versus those of Satyajit Ray. The CPIM versus the Congress party, North Calcutta versus the South. For hours they argue about politics of America, a country in which none of them is eligible to vote.

(Lahiri 2003: 38)

However, Atin is in sharp contrast to the Bengali immigrants portrayed in *The Namesake*, who seem to huddle together to form a little island of Calcutta in the vast foreign land. On the one hand, Atin vehemently refuses to assimilate with the expatriate Bengali group familiar to his friend Siddhartha. This is evident in the scene where on the way back from one weekend Bengali gathering, a Bengali graduate student Nita questions Atin's demeanour, "You are too proud, aren't you? The way you were looking at all of us, it seemed to me that we were all fools and you were the only intelligent person" (Gangopadhyay 1989: 49). She further accuses, "He had no right to insult Santa Boudi; such a nice lady ... he created a farce in the name of eating and left the room while Santa Boudi was singing. Who does that!" (Gangopadhyay 1989: 50). On the other hand, Atin is compelled to distance himself from unknown Bengalis to avoid the risk of his affiliation to the Naxal movement being exposed and his life being endangered, because in New York, which houses a substantial Bengali population, the kin of those killed by the Naxalites back home may well seek revenge. In fact, Siddhartha advises him to move to the mid-West, Arizona or New Mexico, regions which, unlike New York, have a negligible Bengali population, and thus minimise his life risk. Atin, in the first phase of his immigrant life in America, therefore remains an alienated self, who finds no means to alleviate his suffering caused by what Said terms as, "the loss of native hearth and homeland" (Said 2000: 178).

Ralph J. Crane and Radhika Mohanram argue that the trauma of migration involves a physical wrenching from home, language, nation, and the very sense of identity. In their opinion, migration from home, language, familiar landscape, and culture is necessarily

experienced as loss and pain (Crane and Mohanram 2000: ix). Atin initially seems to embody this sense of loss. He feels helplessly trapped in America and suffers from what C. Vijayasree terms as “anxiety arising from a sense of weightlessness, a lack of safe anchorage” in a foreign land (Vijayasree 2000: 126). This leads him to even attempt suicide by jumping off a moving car. At this stage of his existence in America, Atin is not shown to appreciate, even in the very least, the fact that America grants him the freedom and safety, which were jeopardized in India, and further offers the prospect of re-fashioning his future, while as a Naxalite the future that awaited him in India was imprisonment and brutal torture or death. Instead, Atin is psychologically plagued by a deep sense of guilt of betraying the Naxalite ideology and his Naxalite friends by escaping into the safe zone of capitalist America, while back home in West Bengal, the Naxalites continue to face extreme dangers. He is terrified by any news of Naxalite deaths, wondering if his closest friends and comrades Kaushik or Manik-da are dead. A trope common in Bengali Naxalite narratives is a Naxalite betraying fellow Naxalites by leaking secret information to the police, and in exchange, securing his passage to a foreign land at the cost of their lives. Among other several other works, this trope is projected in Bani Basu’s ⁶ novel *Antarghat* through the character of Sumanta Sengupta, and in the movie *Meghnadbadh Rashaya* ⁷ through the figure of Ashimava Bose. Unlike Sumanta and Ashimava, Atin has not literally betrayed anyone or anything associated with the movement. His sense of betrayal stems from his abandonment of the Naxalite cause and his Naxalite friends and seeking safety in a capitalist country in a stark departure from the ideology of the movement. In fact, it is this guilt of betrayal that predominantly conditions Atin’s stubborn refusal to adapt to American life, assimilate with the expatriate Bengali community, and appreciate the possibilities America holds for him.

Atin’s sense of displacement, desperate longing for the world left behind, and guilt of abandoning his political ideology and Naxalite friends is poignantly reflected in the text as he is shown to internalise and thus subconsciously frequently hum the folk song that he one day hears his roommate singing. A song that epitomises the absolute alienation of the individual from the space they inhabit, “You Go Back to land of the Red Hills/the land of the Red Soil/you do not suit this place/do not suit it at all” (Gangopadhyay 1989: 251); the “at all” or absolutely encapsulating Atin’s desperation as well as his guilt. The narrative further emphasises Atin’s acute sense of displacement and desperation by showcasing his irrational determination to abandon the space of safety and prospects - America and return to the very space of life threat - India, which he has succeeded in escaping, once he is able to save enough for his passage money. Atin is even prepared to relinquish prospects of future professional success by quitting the doctoral program at Boston University, if the money is procured prior to his finishing the degree. Sunil Gangopadhyay’s depiction of Atin in this first phase of his immigrant life in America seems to approximate a subject position that Sara Ahmed conceptualises as the “melancholic migrant” (Ahmed 2010).⁸ According to Ahmed, a melancholic migrant is one who cannot dissociate himself/herself from the past of their country of origin, and therefore becomes a veritable cause of concern for the host country in terms of non-assimilation with its ethos. Atin can be regarded as a melancholic migrant as, in his initial months in New York and even in his later years in graduate school, he fails to extricate himself from his Naxalite Indian past and embrace his American present of safety and the promise of future success in America.

Purbo-Paschim Vol II depicts the second phase of Atin’s immigrant life in America as that of the “melancholic migrant” beginning to accept the foreign land as his inevitable destination and thereby initiating the process of acculturation. Sunil Gangopadhyay presents Atin’s romantic relationship with a fellow Bengali graduate student, Sharmila, as the catalyst

to the change in Atin's stance from defiant resistance to American life to accepting America as his present reality. The narrative portrays Sharmila as a character who adheres to the American concept of individual freedom of choice, over traditional Indian mores, which advocate strict regulation of women's sexuality within the institution of marriage. This is evident in that her romantic relationship with Atin in America entails physical intimacy, resulting in pregnancy outside of marriage, which is considered as a lack of propriety according to traditional Indian norms. Sharmila functions as an enabler of safety and rationality for Atin by convincing him to embrace America with its security and prospects over India, where, although by the mid-nineteen seventies the Naxalite movement had ended in failure, anyone who had been associated with the movement was still under life threat. She succeeds in persuading a reluctant Atin to accept the job offer and remain in America post his Ph.D., when Atin grows increasingly despondent at the thought of accepting the job, since it would mean the nullification of his decision of returning to India after obtaining his degree.

In narratives portraying the Indian-American diasporic experience, driving is often projected as a marker of Indian immigrants beginning the process of assimilation into American life. This trope is prominent in Bharati Mukherjee's and Jhumpa Lahiri's works- specific examples being Bharati Mukherjee's novel *Desirable Daughters* and Jhumpa Lahiri's short story "Mrs Sen". In *Desirable Daughters* the protagonist Tara's acquiring the ability to drive serves as a declaration of her successful embracing of America; Lahiri's character Mrs. Sen, however, fails to drive, which indicates her perpetually remaining alienated in America. We see the use of this trope in *Purbo-Paschim Vol II* as well as an indicator of Atin's gradual acceptance of America as his space, in the second phase of his immigrant life, as against his presence as an outsider in discord with America in the first phase. Atin refuses to purchase a car when he is a graduate student, even if that requires walking or cycling in the Boston snow. But he makes this concession for Sharmila, despite having to repeatedly justify to his own conscience that this purchase is not a frivolous indulgence in American excess but is an essentiality of his professional life. Atin's choice of Sharmila, in America, over Oli, his love interest in Calcutta, functions in the text as symbolic of his choice of America over India; this is poignantly depicted in a scene, which plays out in Atin's mind, where Bablu (Atin's pet name) of Calcutta confronts Atin of America.

The shadow answered I am Bablu of Kolkata. Pratap Majumder's son. You are Atin of America; don't you recognize me? Atin answers, why will I not recognize you. I haven't forgotten anything [...]

[Bablu]: Oli? Who is Oli? Your father's friend's daughter; a mere acquaintance isn't it? [...]

[Atin]: Oli is my friend; she will remain my friend [...] Have I ever told her that I will marry her? No [...] Our friendship from our childhood days will remain!

[Bablu]: Does one need to articulate such things? [...] Oli discontinued private tuitions with a music teacher and an English professor only because you insisted. And what about when the two of you were travelling from Memary to Krishnanagar? On the banks of the Ganga in the evening, after crossing the ferry, and again later on the rickshaw, what did you tell Oli, Atin?

[Atin]: Bablu, let go [...]

[Bablu]: That means you don't want to remember Oli anymore.

[Atin]: Get lost Bablu.

(Gangopadhyay 1989: 317)

For Oli America emerges as a signifier of the alien space that deprives her of a seminal aspect of her life - her lover Atin, and which she abandons in the midst of her very first semester in graduate school after becoming aware of Atin's betrayal. In an orthogonal trajectory, Sharmila is able to transform the alien space into her own by successfully carving out a niche for herself in America, personally as well as professionally. Sharmila's pregnancy and Atin's decision to marry her and remain in America signify in the novel his creating a world for himself in America, which excludes forever those that tie him back to his homeland - his parents and friends in Calcutta. His parents are shocked and hurt as he merely conveys the news of his marriage in a letter. Moralists as they are, Atin's closest friend and fellow Naxalites Kaushik and his wife Pompom never approve of his marriage to Sharmila, betraying Oli. Atin's relationship with Sharmila, in the second phase of his journey as an immigrant, thus translates the experience of migrating to America, which Atin with a sense of guilt had earlier perceived as alienation and a painful severing from his roots, into a rite of passage to freedom, safety, and better materialist prospects. Nevertheless, even at the point in the narrative when Atin decides to settle in America, Atin's choice of America over India, unlike that of the Indian-American immigrants in the works of Bharati Mukherjee, Jhumpa Lahiri and Chitra Divakaruni, is not an unqualified choice of the space that offers freedom and materialist prospects over the other which essentially limits him. Sunil Gangopadhyay illustrates its layered nature in that his immigrant character Atin, despite having lived in America for a while by the time of the decision, still perceives America as foreign land. He embraces the safety it offers him solely for the sake of the child to be born, with the hope that one day his child will be able accomplish what he cannot - return to his own country/ his "desh" - a hope that no first generation Indian-American immigrant character of Bharati Mukherjee, Jhumpa Lahiri or Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni is shown to nurture, "Atin cried out 'whether it is a son or a daughter, he/she will never have any restrictions on returning to India. No matter what happens to me, our child will grow up, return to our country and will create a happy, healthy life there. I will live through him/her'" (Gangopadhyay 1989: 517).

If the second phase of Atin's immigrant life is a nuanced illustration of the immigrant beginning to embrace his new world, the third phase depicts the highly complicated and conflicted subject position of the hyphenated Indian-American immigrant. In "Dissemi-Nation: Time, Narrative and the Margins of the Modern Nation," Homi Bhabha contends that the nation's margins, to which diaspora and other minority communities are relegated, are highly complex and flexible recesses of cultural production from where various oppositional practices and analytic capacities can emerge (Bhabha 1992: 310-11). This complexity and flexibility are exemplified in Gangopadhyay's portrayal of a forty-one-year-old Atin in the final section of the novel. In this third phase, Atin apparently seems to have successfully remodelled his life in accordance to demands of the new space of America, and in the process discarded, without any guilt, what acted as impediments to his assimilation in the new milieu - his ideology and his attachment to his parents and friends in India. Yet, Atin's saga of successful pursuit of the American Dream reveals beneath the layer of success the figure of the India-American immigrant consumed by the discontent of eternally lingering in the liminal space of his hyphenated identity, unable to fully belong to either side of the hyphen.

The third phase of Atin's journey as an immigrant pans out in the novel predominantly through four scenarios. His conversation with Siddhartha on his way to the New York airport, his moments of reflection in aloneness at the New York airport while he awaits the flight to Denver, at the Denver airport, and finally at the hotel in Denver. In the conversation with Siddhartha, Atin seems to have completely amalgamated into his adopted world and is

dismissive of any reflection of what is lost by leaving India as irrational nostalgia. Therefore, to Atin, Siddhartha's angst of being circumscribed by a life of relentless pursuit of materialistic pleasures in America, and the thought of once more attempting to settle back in India are "cheap sentiment" (Gangopadhyay 1989: 539); Atin thus sarcastically replies to Siddhartha:

How much did you drink last night? It seems you are still not out of the hangover. Have you forgotten what happened last time? You will indulge in that foolishness once more.
(Gangopadhyay 1989: 538)

Sunil Gangopadhyay projects Atin's disdainful dismissiveness through the Bengali slangs he uses to refer to alcohol and drinking.

Through Atin's musings at the New York airport, Gangopadhyay reveals that the key to his immigrant character's seamless acculturation into American life has been Atin's as well as Siddhartha's failed ventures of settling back in Calcutta with their families, once with the change of government in West Bengal the Naxalites were absolved of all charges against them. Atin ascribes this failure to the dearth of opportunities for professional growth caused by the lack of work ethic, and an overall compromised quality of life in India. At the New York airport, reminiscing about the experience of returning to India, Atin feels relieved that he had not closed the doors of his passage back to America by translating into action his thought of tearing up the Green Card prior to departing for India. To him, Siddhartha's thought of yet again endeavouring to settle in India is a manifestation of his guilt for circumstances he was not in the least responsible for—Siddhartha's father's death in an accident during his parents' visit to America, and his mother's stubborn decision to live alone in Calcutta instead of staying back in America with him and his family.

The scene at the Denver airport at the outset projects Atin as one who has absolutely, and, in fact, without any qualms of conscience, detached himself from his Indian ties, when, upon the receipt of the news of his father being gravely ill, he negates all possibilities of visiting Calcutta by abandoning his work trip. In a selfishly cruel stance, Atin inwardly blames his father for falling ill at a crucial juncture in his career when he is to be rewarded with a significant career rise after the success of the business trip. Internally, Atin wishes that instead of the news of the illness, he had received the news of his father's death, which would have spared him the moral dilemma of having to choose between completing his work trip, and going to Calcutta by abandoning the trip mid-way, and thereby relinquishing the prospects it promises. At this point, Atin seems to emblemize Bharati Mukherjee's real-life self-description in her essay "On Being an American Writer", where she claims, "I came to a profound conclusion. I was no longer Indian in mind or spirit - [and thus] the multifarious tyrannies of a loving family [back home] was no longer tolerable to me" (Mukherjee 2025). In a similar vein, it is apparent that Atin's connection to his parents is no longer a bond of love, but is rather a bondage of responsibility. A responsibility which is discharged, as his thought process reveals, by him sending a hundred dollars every month to his mother, with the value of the dollar being on a rise. Atin muses, "There must not be any financial constraints; the bank has a standing instruction to send a hundred dollars to Ma each month. A hundred dollars amounts to twelve hundred rupees, and the value of the dollar is constantly rising" (Gangopadhyay 1989: 606). Therefore, to him the prospect of his aged father's death is also not a tragedy but is only a natural culmination of life. He argues to himself:

I would have remained calm had I even received the news of Baba's passing away. Baba is almost seventy; he has led life on his own terms. We will all have to die one day [...]

With adequate medical care he may live for another ten to twelve years [...] Ma is expecting me to visit and take care of things [...] There is nothing for me to do there. She has adequate financial resources [...] Sharmila is thinking I am disturbed by this news. All I am feeling is a dilemma. Visiting India, amidst this important assignment is a hassle [...] Had Baba breathed his last, there would have been no rush.

(Gangopadhyay 1989: 610–11)

However, that the India-American immigrant experience is not a unidimensional choice of one world over the other is brought to light by Gangopadhyay in the Denver airport scene itself. In her criticism of the projection of the female Indian immigrants' unqualified choosing of America over India in Bharati Mukherjee's novels, Brinda Bose argues "what gets covered in the flurry of change and action is the conflict and confusion of the 'whole cross-cultural business' [...] the trauma of getting used to the idea that one is not going to be completely at home in either place" (Bose 1993: 49). This trauma finds expression through Atin. Amidst thoughts that reflect his complete engrossment in the pursuit of the American Dream, Atin, while still at the Denver airport, is suddenly jolted by his mind conjuring up the image of his mother in widow's white all alone in a nursing home in Calcutta, "The image made him shiver; forty-one-year-old, confident, success-hunter Atin Majumder metamorphosed into a young boy. He wanted to run to his mother" (Gangopadhyay 1989: 611). A self and career centric Atin, who had moments before justified to himself his decision of not visiting his sick father, drawing upon his father's history of failing to reach his grandfather in his deathbed, is shown to be overpowered by a feeling of helplessness and an acute sense of alienation and isolation, "In this country no one spares more than a glance for strangers; no one takes a peek to into another's mind without a reason. How helplessly alone is Atin in this vast airport" (Gangopadhyay 1989: 611). Atin, thereafter, is portrayed as desperate to reach his father, while he is still alive, and clear all misunderstandings with a response that contradicts and complicates his earlier image of fully and comfortably assimilating into the life of his chosen country:

I must let Baba know [...] even before joining the Ph.D. I wanted to return; you all only forbade me [...] even today I do not like living in this foreign land; I have not developed roots in this country; [...] Sharmila too, after so many years, has not come to like the life of this country. She is ready to return any day. But our children refuse to go. India is not their country; they feel no connection to the land or its people.

(Gangopadhyay 1989: 615)

Sunil Gangopadhyay thus projects that the greatest irony of Atin's Indian-American hyphenated subject position is the fact that the very child for whose future prospect of returning to India, Atin had once embraced the safety of America, eventually becomes the cause of his inability to leave America for India.

Arindam Ghosh claims that although Atin becomes successful, "fulfilling the stereotypical American dream of prosperity, at another level he is disenchanted by his corporate-suburban life, and quite lost in terms of [...] purpose" (Ghosh 2015: 33). However, I argue that Atin's disillusionment is not the outcome of a dissatisfied professional life or a lack of purpose. It develops from his inability to completely adhere to either side of his hyphenated identity. Sunil Gangopadhyay further delineates, through the scenarios at the Denver hotel, how Atin suffers inwardly due to his feelings of being an outsider both in his adopted country and in his country of origin. This, as is evident from the portrayal of Atin, is a marked deviation

from his outer image of being ensconced in the American professional sphere as Dr. Atin Majumder and in the personal space of his Indian-American family and the Indian-American expatriate community of New York/New Jersey. At the Denver airport, Atin's thought of what is essential for him to clarify to his father serves a disclosure of him not being able to integrate fully into American life and remaining an outsider in his adopted world. Alone at the hotel, he admits to himself that the real reason, which he has never before acknowledged to others or even to his own self, of his inability to re-settle in India with his family was the feeling of being an outsider in his own country. This sense of being perpetually alienated from his former world in Calcutta was generated in him particularly by the responses of two people who had been integral to this world for him - his erstwhile best friend and comrade Kaushik and his former love interest Oli. While Kaushik had displayed indifference, Oli had adopted a very polite and yet subtle unforgiving stance towards him. As Atin confesses to himself, he had been prepared for the dearth of professional opportunities and the discomforts of day to day life in India, the causes he had cited for his permanent return to America. However, what he had been truly unprepared for and had failed to accept was the rejection by Oli and Kaushik of him as one of their own:

A hurt Atin had physically shaken Kaushik and asked "why are you treating me like an outsider? Do I smell of America? Are you still angry that I could not be there for you when you were in grave danger? I too have faced severe danger alone." Kaushik had replied with a pale smile: "It's nothing like that. Can you leave everything and come and stay with us in Jhargram's Binpur? We can communicate like before, only when we are at the same level as before."

(Gangopadhyay 1989: 613)

As he writes in his autobiography *Ardhek Jibon [Half a Life]* Sunil Gangopadhyay himself had been apprehensive of being denied his former place among his friends in Calcutta, upon his return from America (Gangopadhyay 2002: 264). What had been only an apprehension for the author, is transformed by him into a reality for his character Atin, rendering Atin an outsider in his native world.

The narrative represents the space of in-betweenness of identities as virtually an entrapment for the Indian-American diasporic subject Atin, once he becomes cognizant of the fact that as an American citizen he can no longer visit India without a visa. In his tumultuous state of mind, Atin seemed not to remember, or as Gangopadhyay, hinting at a doubt at the obvious, writes "perhaps did not want to remember" this aspect of his immigrant existence (Gangopadhyay 1989: 620). This reality of Atin's subject position is laid bare to him through the remark of Atin's co-worker Jim. To Atin's agitated declaration that he would resign from his job to reach his father at the earliest, Jim responds:

Your intention is noble, but you don't really have an option. You think you are Indian, but you are no longer an Indian [...] your passport is American. You need a visa to go to India. Everything is closed on the weekend; you won't be able to get a visa.

(Gangopadhyay 1989: 619)

Further, Jim humorously adds, "Atin Majumder you are trapped; you are an American now" (Gangopadhyay 1989: 620). Through the character of Atin, Sunil Gangopadhyay seems to suggest that no matter how ardently the immigrant seeks to remould himself in his adopted world, relegating the past in the native land to oblivion, he can never disentangle himself from

this past. In a state of acute helplessness, which is caused by a sense of his inability to resist virtual confinement in America, what had ceased to concern Atin in the life he had created for himself in America returns to haunt him. Once again he feels guilty of having failed his own in India - his friends with whom he once shared an ideology, Oli who had loved him, and his parents - by not being present to support any of them. Like his initial days in America, after decades in the country, alone in the Denver hotel, Atin is yet again consumed with remorse at the thought that he is perceived as selfish by those he has left behind in India – “Kaushik and Pompom believe he has stayed back in America for the love of dollars and trivial material comforts; ‘Ma [...] Do you think so too?’” (Gangopadhyay 1989: 621). He remembers his dead elder brother Piklu, who had died trying to save him from drowning; Atin holds himself responsible for his brother’s death. Atin reflects on the murder he had committed; he realises that it was his desperate attempt to save the Naxalite leader Manika-da, whom he had subconsciously accorded the position of his dead elder brother. Thus the murder was his subconscious endeavour to atone for the death of his own brother by saving Manik-da from his attacker. Atin feels he has even killed the person Oli was in her youth by discarding her from his life. A despairing and vulnerable Atin draws out from the deep recesses of his mind yet another never disclosed but seminal truth, which has governed the course of his life. He recalls that his relationship with Sharmila had been initiated through an act of physical intimacy with her while he was hiding in Jamshedpur after committing the murder. However, the reason he had engaged in this act, which resulted in a betrayal of Oli, was his mistaking Sharmila to be Oli in a state of feverish delirium. The narratorial voice states, “No one knows this. He couldn’t tell Oli about this later as he didn’t want to insult her” (Gangopadhyay 1989: 621).

In the Indian-American immigrant narratives of Bharati Mukherjee, Chitra Divakaruni and Jhumpa Lahiri, professional success brings satisfaction and fulfilment to the lives of the immigrant men and endorses their choice of an immigrant life in America. Mukherjee’s and Divakaruni’s women relish the opportunity of self-remaking that America, devoid of the conservatism of Indian society, offers them, and willingly detach themselves from their Indian roots. Lahiri’s women characters like Ashima (*Namesake*) and Aparna (“Hell-Heaven”) eventually come to accept that they belong at once to both India and America, and without either, their self-definition is incomplete. Hence, the hyphen in their identity translates into “and,” resolving the sense of conflict between its two sides. However, in Sunil Gangopadhyay’s narrative, despite achieving professional and personal success in America, the hyphen in Atin’s Indian-American identity remains a marker of his existence in a liminal space between two worlds, problematized by a sense of guilt of betraying his own and conditioned by much that Atin has failed to articulate.

The final image of Atin in the novel is him, in a naked state, lying all alone on the fire escape on the roof of the hotel in Denver. Atin is shown for the final time in the novel as being detached from everything and everyone in America or India and not answering the phone but wondering whether it is Sharmila calling him from New Jersey or Oli from Calcutta returning the call he had made to her, after more than a decade, to inquire about his father.

Who is calling Sharmila or Oli? Is his father alive or not? Why does he even need to know? Two oceans stretch on two sides; Atin has no ticket, no visa. He won't be able to jump and cross the ocean like Hanuman. There is no point in explaining his situation to anyone. He is caged. It's of no use knowing whether his father is alive or not. There are no clothes on his body; he is almost suspended in space. He is almost like an animal [...] like the ancestor of humankind i.e. a monkey. He cannot be categorised as Indian or American.

(Gangopadhyay 1989: 622)

Such a culmination of the character arc of Atin signifies his absolutely alienated suspension in the conflicted in-between space of his hyphenated Indian-American identity, with the two women, Oli and Sharmila, representing the two sides of the hyphen.

3 Conclusion

In his autobiography *Ardhek Jibon [Half a Life]*, Sunil Gangopadhyay mentions observing himself naked in the mirror at a point when he was torn between remaining in America and returning to India and how that had helped him to arrive at the decision of leaving America for India (Gangopadhyay 2002: 266-67). It is interesting to note that in the novel, Atin's nakedness is displayed at a moment which defines that he can never belong wholly either to India or to America and must perennially linger, isolated and dissatisfied, in the liminal space of his hyphenated Indian-American identity. In this final depiction of Atin, Sunil Gangopadhyay seems to put Atin beyond human parameters into the realm of animalization, first through the image of the Monkey-God "Hanuman," and then through the image of a "monkey." Atin is not just neither Indian nor American; he seems to be alienated from humankind itself.

In *Purbo-Paschim Vol II*, through the character of Atin Majumder, Sunil Gangopadhyay thus portrays Indian-American diasporic identity formation as a complex multi-phased and multi-layered process, which eludes any simplistic categorization of belonging fully to either side of the hyphen. The first phase of Atin's immigrant life in America is projected as one of painful exile and alienation caused by the removal from what is his own - his homeland and its people. The second phase depicts Atin's reluctant acceptance of America as his inevitable destination, and the initiation of his acculturation into American life. The third phase initially appears to be completely orthogonal to the first two; in this phase, at the beginning, Atin seems to have completely assimilated into the American world, dissociating himself from the world of his origins. Yet, this phase gradually unravels the complicated and conflicted subject position of the hyphenated Indian-American immigrant. It becomes obvious that no matter how actively Atin has striven to define and redefine himself, Atin's Indian roots and his choice of being an American citizen never come together harmoniously to define him. They remain conflicted and suspend him perpetually, all by himself, in the problematic in-between space of his hyphenated identity.

Thus not only is Calcutta based Bengali writer Sunil Gangopadhyay's exploration of the issue of cross-cultural migration from India to America, in a Bengali novel, an interesting rarity, his depiction of the diasporic subject position is also distinct from that of Indian-American writers like Jhumpa Lahiri, Bharati Mukherjee, and Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni. Professional success endorses the choice of America over India for the male characters in the works of Lahiri, Mukherjee and Divakaruni. Mukherjee and Divakaruni's women find fulfillment in the freedom of choices that America offers to them in contrast to the constrictions imposed by the conservative Indian society; Lahiri's women characters finally embrace an

identity that is at once Indian and American. In contrast, Sunil Gangopadhyay's Atin remains suspended forever in the liminal space of his hyphenated Indian-American identity. Atin lacks stable affiliation to either side of the hyphen and emerges as a figure of the diasporic individual who is alienated and isolated both in his country of origin and his adopted country, to the extent that he seems to be alienated from humankind itself.

Notes

1 Sunil Gangopadhyay (1934- 2012), among several other awards, was the recipient of the Bankim Puraskar in 1982, the Sahitya Akademi Award in 1985, and the Ananda Puraskar twice in 1972 and 1989. Gangopadhyay was the executive board member of Sahitya Akademi, New Delhi from 1998-2002.

2 For further discussion on these aspects of Gangopadhyay's writings, see Goswami (2012), Chakrabarti (1991), Chatterjee (2009), and Bhattacharya (2013)

3 For further discussion, see Singh (2014), and Ghosh (2015).

4 For further discussion, see Singh (2014), and Ghosh (2015).

5 An English translation of volume *Purbo-Paschim Volume I* was published in 2000, and an English translation of *Volume II* was published in 2004. However, the translations for the quotes from the novel used in this paper have been done by me.

6 Bani Basu (1939–) is one of the most powerful contemporary women voices in Bengali literature, who has received popular as well as critical acclaim. She has to her credit 12 novels, and several short stories and essays. Among other awards, Bani Basu was the recipient of the Ananda Puraskar in 1997, Bankim Puraskar in 1998, and Sahitya Akademi Award in 2010.

7 Meghnadbad Rahasya is a 2017 Bengali film of the thriller genre directed by Anik Dutta.

8 For further discussion see Ahmed (2010).

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Richard III: Constructing a Master Manipulator

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Abstract

This paper examines the construction of master manipulator traits of the character of Richard, Duke of Gloucester, over the course of two of Shakespeare's plays, through the textual indicators of character, as presented in Rimmon-Kenan's Narrative Fiction. Special focus is put on speech and action. Richard's actions in Henry VI set the stage for him to become a Machiavellian political actor and foreshadow his later villainy. His ambitions in this play are obvious but not fully enacted through direct lies or intricate plotting, whereas in Richard III, he becomes a theatrical mastermind and one of the most brilliant Shakespearean villains.

Keywords: Richard III, Henry VI, Shakespeare, Renaissance drama, textual indicators of character.

1 Introduction

1.1. William Shakespeare's history plays

Discussing literary characters is closely linked to discussing literature in general, and it is difficult to speak about literary figures without referencing some of the characters introduced during the Renaissance period by William Shakespeare. Some of them exist only within literature, while others are based on actual historical individuals.

Shakespeare's history plays, two of which are *Henry VI* and *Richard III* that we will discuss in this paper, primarily explore the English monarchs and political conflicts of medieval England, especially during the Hundred Years' War and the Wars of the Roses, which are described as "a tumultuous time" (Gillum 2014: 1). These two plays present Richard as Duke of Gloucester and later King of England. Taking that into consideration, it is the aim of this paper to examine the evolution of his character through certain textual indicators which are usually not applied to plays, which will be further discussed in the methodological section of the paper.

It is well known that one of the plays at the centre of this paper, *The Tragedy of Richard the Third*, is based largely on Thomas More's *The History of King Richard III* (1557). Shakespeare adopted More's depiction of Richard's villainy. Moore (2013: 7) describes the king in the following terms:

Richard the third son, of whom we now entreat, was in wit and courage equal with either of them, in body and prowess far under them both, little of stature, ill featured of limbs, crook-backed, his left shoulder much higher than his right, hard favoured of visage, and such as is in states called warly, in other men otherwise, he was malicious, wrathful, envious, and from afore his birth, ever forward.

More's Richard is not only a criminal, but also "an unparalleled actor who perfected the political skill of manipulation, adopting various identities to conceal his true thirst for power

and to undermine the importance of family values and conventional morality” (Kostić 2014b: 1). Particular emphasis is placed on his deformity, both physical and mental.

As Veselin Kostić (1994: 177, my translation) observes,

Richard III brings forth a new art of characterization and represents the first dramatic character in English literature who was imagined and realized as a complete psychological being, determined not only by self-presentation and the comments of other characters, but also by more refined dramatic means, such as an individualized way of expression, thought and reactions to external events. In this sense, Richard III represents a great improvement over Shakespeare’s earlier history plays

which makes it a compelling subject of analysis.

Although based on historical events and figures, Shakespeare’s history plays are ultimately works of fiction, prioritizing dramatic effect and compelling narrative over absolute historical accuracy. As Milena Kaličanin (2017: 43, my translation) notes,

all of Shakespeare’s historical plays represent a link between fact and fiction, history and imagination, where the sharp difference between the creative artist and the rational historian, which the famous Renaissance poet Philip Sidney talks about in *Defence of Poetry*, is actually not lost, and the qualities of the artist and the historian are combined to create a special genre typical of Elizabethan England.

1.2 Richard III as a historical figure

It is important to recognize that Shakespeare’s Richard III is based on the actual King Richard III, whose historical persona differs significantly from the character portrayed in the play. As Wolfgang Hermann Clemen (1954: 247) notes, “the relation between the originality of a dramatist and the tradition from which his work derives is an interesting subject.” Moreover, according to Caroline Augusta Halsted (1844: v), “the genius of Shakespeare seized upon the history of Richard the Third as a vacant possession, and peopled it with beings who have, indeed, historic names, but whose attributed descriptions and actions are, for the most part, the mere imaginings of the bard.”

The public perception of Richard is based almost entirely on Shakespeare’s character, presented in these two of his historical plays, so it is important to note the historical facts as well. Richard reigned as King of England from the 26th of June 1483 until his death in 1485 and was the last monarch of the Plantagenet dynasty. His defeat and death at the Battle of Bosworth Field is considered to be the end of the Middle Ages in England and, according to some interpretations, marked the end of the Wars of the Roses. Regarding Richard III’s reign, Dorte Hasberg Zirak-Schmidt (2018: 21) writes that “to the Elizabethan public, there was no monarch in recent history with such a dark reputation as Richard III: usurpation, tyranny, fratricide, and even incest were among his many alleged crimes, and a legacy of cunning dissimulation and cynical Machiavellianism had clung to him since his early biographers’ descriptions of him.” The question of deformity is particularly intriguing, especially as a probable cause of his villainous character. In Shakespeare’s plays, Richard is portrayed as a hunchback with a withered arm, a depiction believed to have been created to symbolize the corruption of his mind. According to Milena Kostić (2015: 1, my translation), this physical distortion serves as the “embodiment” of his moral deformity. However, the discovery of Richard’s remains in 2012 revealed a pronounced curvature of the spine consistent with

idiopathic adolescent-onset scoliosis. Contemporary descriptions that mention “unequal shoulders, the right higher and the left lower” align with the presence of right-sided scoliosis (University of Leicester n.d.). However, there seems to be no evidence supporting the existence of a withered arm.

2 Methodological approach

Shlomith Rimmon-Kenan’s narratological theory of characterization has been shown to be effective for the examination of characters in all periods, so it can be effectively applied to our Shakespearean sixteenth century plays. In addition to that, it is a method typically used for the analysis of prose texts, so applying it to a play may bring forward new insights about the way a character, in this case Richard III, was built. To facilitate understanding, the main ideas and the method of character synthesis presented by Rimmon-Kenan (1991: 59–71) in chapter five of *Narrative Fiction* will be summarised here. Rimmon-Kenan stresses that within any narrative, a character is a construct assembled by the reader from various indicators throughout the text. While any textual element may serve as a character indicator, some elements are more closely linked to characterization. These indicators fall largely into two types: direct definition and indirect presentation: “In the first case, the trait is named using an adjective (he is good-hearted), an abstract noun (his goodness knew no bounds), another kind of noun (she was a real bitch), or part of speech (he loves only himself)” (Rimmon-Kenan 1991: 59–60). In the second type, the traits are not explicitly stated but are conveyed through examples, allowing the reader to infer them. Not every naming of a character’s qualities constitutes direct definition; such definition counts only when it comes from the text’s most authoritative voice (Rimmon-Kenan 1991: 60). In prose fiction, this is typically the narrator. Because dramatic texts lack a conventional narrator, this paper will also explore how direct definition operates within plays.

Indirect presentation occurs when traits are revealed through action rather than directly stated. Both one-time actions and habitual behaviour can imply character traits. Single actions tend to reveal dynamic aspects of a character, often connected to turning points in the plot, whereas habitual actions suggest more stable qualities. Although a one-time action may not reflect consistency, it can reveal something more significant than routine behaviours. Actions may be categorized into acts of commission (what the character does), acts of omission (what the character fails to do even though they should), and contemplated acts (intentions that remain unrealized). A character’s speech, be it dialogue or thought, also serves as an indicator, through both content and form. What one character says about another can reflect not only the target but also the speaker. “The form and style of speech are common means of characterization in texts where characters’ language is individualized and distinguished from that of the narrator” (Rimmon-Kenan, 1991: 64). Style may suggest geographical origin, social background, or profession, and it may also reveal individual traits. It should be noted that, as per Norman Francis Blake (1983: 48), we should hesitate to interpret the meanings of Shakespeare’s words too rigorously because they may have been chosen for quite different reasons: “the stylistic level appropriate to the context and the effect of the sound pattern... Equally he may have been less worried than we are by word-substitution made by actors and editors provided the sound-pattern and rhythm were maintained.” Nonetheless, speech inevitably contributes to characterization, particularly when supported by other indicators. As Sébastien Mercier (2019: 206) points out, “speech and stagecraft create a dramatic reality.”

Physical appearance also contributes to characterization. One should distinguish between features beyond the character's control (e.g. height) and those partly controlled (e.g. clothing or hairstyle). Sometimes appearance speaks for itself; other times, the narrator explicitly links appearance to a particular trait, turning it into a disguised form of direct definition. The character's surroundings, such as their home, town, or social environment, can also function as metonymic indicators.

This method of characterization will be applied to the figure of Richard III as a character in two of Shakespeare's plays that he is presented in. According to Tamara Kostić Pahnoglu (2024: 15), this approach "is appropriate for characters that don't differ a lot from real persons," and Richard III, despite Shakespeare's modifications, indeed was a historical figure.

3 The evolution of Richard III through the textual indicators of character in Henry VI and Richard III

3.1 The timeline

Chronologically, the events of *Henry VI* come before those of *Richard III*. In *Henry VI*, Richard becomes Duke of Gloucester, while in *Richard III* the plot follows his rise from Duke to King of England. As Richard gains more power and acquires a higher position, his Machiavellian tendencies become more prominent. However, while he is presented as a master manipulator in *Richard III*, there is evidence of him being cunning, selfish, and calculated even in *Henry VI*. Thus, the aim of this paper is to examine whether the textual indicators of character presented by Rimmon-Kenan showcase the evolution of his character, or more precisely, of his villainy, and in what way.

3.2 The beginning of the manipulation in Henry VI part 3

It is obvious that Richard is manipulative in *Henry VI part 3*, but his manipulations are fewer, cruder, and less sustained than in *Richard III*. He is still more of an apprentice villain than the mastermind he becomes later. According to Michael Alan Hicks (1986: 2), it is before his ascension to the throne, as Duke of Gloucester, that Richard "formed habits, patterns of conduct, attitudes and political policies that were unlikely to be changed by his promotion." Therefore, his behaviour in *Henry VI* sets the stage for him becoming the villain that he is recognised as in *Richard III*.

Most of the information the readers get in *Henry VI* could be considered direct definition, because Richard does not begin to express his villainy by outwardly lying to others very often yet. It should be noted that as plays, these texts offer no direct definition in the typical sense, as there is no narrator. Therefore, the moments when Richard is alone on stage and sharing his thought with the audience could be considered as a form of direct definition. It is interesting to note that, as per Lisa Hopkins (2024: 2), "we must not assume that we are being given direct access to a character's thoughts" during soliloquies, due to the fact that the character is performing, in the sense that they are speaking those words aloud. However, for the purposes of this paper, it can be assumed that the characters are being truthful with the audience. In fact, in *Richard III*, Richard even, as Siobhán Keenan (2017: 28) notes, "invites the audience to be complicit in his plans."

In Henry VI, there are mostly scenes which could be thought of as direct definition and indirect presentation through the means of action, which show Richard's manipulative tendencies and intentions. One of the most important and crucial scenes is his soliloquy in Act 3 Scene 2. This monologue reveals many important traits of Richard's character and foreshadows his behaviour in *Richard III*. When Richard says, "And yet I know not how to get the crown, For many lives stand between me and home" (3.2.174-175), he is clearly stating his ambition and his plan to find a way to ascend to the throne, which he eventually succeeds in *Richard III*. The most famous part of this monologue, "Why, I can smile, and murder whiles I smile, And cry 'Content' to that which grieves my heart, And wet my cheeks with artificial tears..." (3.2.184-186), is the most obvious representation of Richard's manipulative nature and his mastery of emotional deception. What he already intends to do, and expands upon later, is controlling how others perceive him, regardless of his true intentions. Another notable part of the soliloquy is "And frame my face to all occasions" (3.2.187), where he expresses social adaptability, i.e. the ability to become what others need him to be and gain their trust, in order to use it for his own personal gain. Finally, Richard states, "I'll make my heaven to dream upon the crown" (3.2.170), which is a full declaration of his ambition. According to Lenna Magnusson (2013: 32), "giving utterance to wishes and desires is fundamental to the language of *Richard III*."

In Act 2 Scene 1, Richard says "I cannot joy, until I be resolved Where our right valiant father is become." (2.1.9-10), thus presenting himself as the committed brother and son, an image that later allows him to operate without suspicion. He reinforces his position within the winning faction and plants seeds of loyalty to Edward, not out of genuine allegiance, but to advance his own influence. Act 3 Scene 3 is an excellent example of omission, an action that a character fails to complete even though they should have done it. This is the scene where Edward is wooing Lady Grey, and it is precisely Richard's silence and restraint that show his true intentions. Warwick is not present in the scene, and Richard is one of the witnesses. Even though the marriage will clearly anger Warwick and fracture alliances, Richard does not stop Edward. He seems to be allowing political damage to occur because it serves his long-term goals. In this scene, he is perceptive and shows that he knows how to use a situation that he finds himself in for his own gain. Finally, Act 5 Scene 6, where he kills king Henry, shows both Richard's ruthlessness and his ambition. While he stabs the king, he says "Down, down to hell; and say I sent thee thither - I that have neither pity, love nor fear" (5.6.68-69), showing cold-blooded intent, as well as the fact that he sees murder simply as a tool for achieving his political aims. This scene can be considered an example of Richard acting on his previously stated intention to make the pursuit of the crown his dream. After the murder of king Henry, there is, according to Alvin B. Kernan (1954: 433), "no true peace since Richard, now Duke of Gloucester and Richard III to be, is already intriguing against his brothers."

3.3 *The culmination of manipulation*

Richard's manipulative abilities reach their highest point in *Richard III*. His deceptive nature is stated more clearly in this play, as even Richard himself, in the famous opening soliloquy, reveals to the audience that he is "determined to prove a villain" (1.1.30). As Richard familiarises the audience with his plans in the soliloquy, it seems as if he is almost manipulating them as well, due to the fact that the audience starts rooting for the villain and that, as Keenan (2017: 28) notes, Richard "invites the audience to be complicit in his plans." "Regarding

‘villain’, for example, it is strange that the villain of the story is not only the protagonist but also the unquestionable monopolist of the reader’s sympathy” (Calvillo 2017: 142, my translation). The opening soliloquy is an excellent example of direct definition as an indicator of character, as Richard takes on the role of the narrator and reveals his villainous nature.

In addition to that, the wooing of Lady Anne in Act 1 Scene 2 exemplifies Richard’s manipulative actions. He meets Lady Anne as she follows the coffin of King Henry VI, whom Richard had murdered along with her husband, Prince Edward. At the beginning of the scene she hates him, but by the end of it she is willing to marry him, which shows the extent of Richard’s manipulation. He essentially blames Lady Anne for his murdering the king and prince, saying “Your beauty was the cause of that effect, Your beauty, that did haunt me in my sleep” (1.2.130-131). He stages a performance of remorse and fakes humility, telling her “Lo, here I lend thee this sharp-pointed sword, Which if thou please to hide in this true breast And let the soul forth that adareth thee, I lay it naked to the deadly stroke” (1.2.191-194). This might be considered emotional coercion, as Richard knows that she will not opt to kill him. Once Anne leaves, he enjoys a private moment of triumph because he managed to convince her to marry him. In that moment he speaks to the audience: “Was ever woman in this humour wooed? Was ever woman in this humour won?” (1.2.247-248). In that way Richard confirms that everything he did was calculated.

Richard’s manipulation is most clearly revealed through his habitual use of lies, which function as indirect presentation both through speech and repeated action. From the opening of the play, he openly deceives others, claiming loyalty to the king and insisting “we speak no treason,” while simultaneously plotting against those closest to him (1.1.94). His promise to Clarence that he will “deliver you or else lie for you” is particularly revealing, as he is already planning Clarence’s death (1.1.118). Richard repeatedly disguises his deceit behind claims of honesty, presenting himself as a “plain man” incapable of flattery or deception, even as he manipulates nearly every character around him (1.3.52). As Kostić (2014a: 5) notes, Richard “portrays his outward show of morality as a well-rehearsed act necessary in order to attain his political goals.” This pattern continues throughout the play, from his feigned humility before his mother and the court, to his betrayal of Buckingham and his calculated guidance of the young prince toward imprisonment in the Tower. His public grief over Hastings’ execution and his repeated refusals of the crown further illustrate how Richard uses false emotion and staged reluctance to shape others’ perceptions. Taken together, these examples show that lying is not incidental but central to Richard’s character, establishing manipulation as his primary means of gaining and maintaining power.

Richard’s lies not only show his habitual deceit but also highlight his skill in acting, which is central to his success as a manipulator. His deception works because he convinces others he is sincere, loyal, or humble when it suits him. Clarence’s inability to suspect Richard of plotting his death illustrates this perfectly; as Tamara Karanović (2021: 30) notes, it is “the best evidence of the success of Richard’s hypocrisy and manipulation.” Speech is a key part of this strategy. As María Macias-Borrego (2025: 1) points out, “speech acts—encompassing not just spoken words, but also the surrounding context—are crucial for understanding Richard’s ability to deceive, manipulate, and persuade.” These carefully crafted words show what Anne Sophie Refskou (2021: 122) calls Richard’s “rhetorical dexterity,” allowing him to shape how others see him and maintain control through language rather than force.

Richard’s manipulation is further revealed through his selective use of abusive language in the function of speech as an indicator of character. In Act 1, Scene 3, he refers to Queen Margaret as a “thou hateful, withered hag” and a “foul, wrinkled witch” (1.3.225-1.3.168),

while in Act 4, Scene 4 he calls Queen Elizabeth as a “relenting fool and shallow, changing woman” (4.4.454). He treats his nephews similarly in Act 4, Scene 2 by calling them “bastards” and wishing them dead (4.2.20), and in Act 1, Scene 3 he curses the court with “a plague upon you all!” (1.3.60). It seems that these moments of verbal aggression occur when Richard is speaking in situations where his hostility carries no political cost. In contrast, when he requires the trust of others, Richard adopts a façade of politeness and humility. This contrast demonstrates that his civility is not natural but performative, revealing language itself as a tool of manipulation through which Richard conceals his intentions and controls how others perceive him.

David Daiches (1969: 250) observes that Richard’s “psychology is far from simple,” a complexity that becomes especially visible in the dream sequence of Act 5, Scene 3. Throughout the play, Richard secures power by manipulating others through language, performance, and emotional deception. Since the dream originates in Richard’s own mind, the speech of the ghosts can be understood as expressing Richard’s suppressed recognition of the consequences of his manipulative actions. Their repeated wishes that he “despair and die” and their desire to “sit heavy on [his] soul tomorrow” articulate a judgment that Richard has successfully concealed from others (5.3.135-124). The ghosts of the princes, in particular, accuse him of causing his own “ruin, shame, and death,” suggesting an internal acknowledgment that his rise has been built on calculated deception and betrayal. This awareness surfaces more explicitly in Richard’s waking soliloquy later in the same scene. His cry, “O coward conscience, how dost thou afflict me!”, followed by confusion shown by saying “I love myself... I rather hate myself... I am a villain. Yet I lie; I am not”, reveals a mind struggling to maintain the self-image that has enabled his manipulation of others (5.3.191, 199-203). As Kostić (2014a: 6) notes, the broken and opposing phrases “reflect Richard’s shattered confidence”. The significance of this speech lies in showing that Richard recognizes the falseness of the persona he has constructed. The psychological breakdown therefore exposes not only guilt, but an implicit awareness that his power has depended on sustained manipulation; an awareness that ultimately undermines his ability to continue deceiving either others or himself.

4 Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to examine which textual indicators of character, according to Rimmon-Kenan’s narratology theory, are used by Shakespeare to exemplify the evolution of the character of Richard as a master manipulator in his plays *Henry VI part 3* and *Richard III*.

As we have shown above, the direct definition is present in both plays, as the presence of a narrator did not prove crucial for the inclusion of this type of indicator in a text. It is exemplified mostly through Richard’s soliloquies and the information he gives the audience about himself. As for indirect presentation, a very important indicator of Richard’s manipulative character are his actions. His actions stay consistently manipulative, although the extent of the manipulation increases. Speech is an important indicator of character as well, taking into consideration both the way Richard addresses other people, and what they have to say about him. External appearance is relevant only if we consider his physical deformity as motivation for his actions, while the environment is mostly not relevant in this case.

In conclusion, there are textual indicators of character, mostly direct definition and indirect presentation through action, in *Henry VI* that point out Richard’s manipulative

tendencies and lay the groundwork for his evolution as a villain. When he does interact manipulatively in this play, it tends to be opportunistic, taking advantage of others' conflicts rather than constructing elaborate traps. However, there is a wider variety of textual indicators in *Richard III* which indicate the same traits to a deeper extent. What can be concluded from that fact is that the presence of those indicators confirms that the traits of his character are consistent, as well as that his character did evolve, as exemplified by the larger number of indicators in the play which follows the later period of his life.

Applying Rimmon-Kenan's narratological framework shows that Richard's manipulation is not limited to a few moments of obvious villainy but is built into the structure of the plays through repeated and increasingly complex character indicators. The movement from more opportunistic manipulation in *Henry VI, Part 3* to deliberate and self-aware deception in *Richard III* does not represent a change in Richard's basic character, but rather a strengthening of traits that are already present. As the plays progress, Richard relies more heavily on soliloquies, carefully chosen language, and deliberate self-presentation, suggesting that manipulation becomes not just a political strategy, but the main way through which he understands power and himself. Tracing these indicators across both plays therefore shows that Richard's development as a master manipulator is gradual, consistent, and clearly supported by the text.

Finally, after tracing the character of Richard III across these two plays, the findings demonstrate, through a methodological lens not typically applied to plays, that character continuity is present. His evolution is never a departure from his true self. Applying Rimmon-Kenan's textual indicators allows us to see how Shakespeare constructs a consistently recognizable, yet dynamically developing persona.

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BOOK REVIEW

Literary Theory: The Basics (Fourth Edition)

Hans Bertens: Routledge (Taylor and Francis Group), 2024, 266 pp.

In contemporary humanities discourse, the term theory frequently evokes a polarized response: it is viewed as a liberatory critical tool capable of uncovering societal power structures, yet also seen as an intimidating labyrinth of esoteric jargon. Hans Bertens's *Literary Theory: The Basics*, now in its updated fourth edition, attempts to negotiate this dialectic by providing a structured guide to literary studies. Bertens, known as a Professor Emeritus of Comparative Literature at Utrecht University, brings his background in the field to this task. His previous works, such as *The Idea of the Postmodern: A History*, demonstrate a capacity for synthesizing dense theoretical frameworks into comprehensible prose. In this monograph, Bertens aims to show how literary theory and literary practice are connected. The book contextualizes theory as an academic discipline that requires ideological understanding. By tracing the evolution of literary criticism from the mid-twentieth century's linguistic shift to the digital humanities, it attempts to clarify theoretical paradigms and present theory as a functional tool for interpreting literature.

Physically, the book is published by Routledge within "The Basics" series, which aims to provide accessible overviews of fundamental subjects. It spans approximately 266 pages, concluding an index that facilitates the navigation of terminology and historical concepts. It is single authored by Bertens, though it references numerous critics and writers to build its historical narratives. The volume is divided into the core chapters, an introductory preface, and an organized bibliography. The book does not rely on visual aids; there are no images, charts, or tables within the chapters broken down into demarcated subsections. A practical feature of the book is the inclusion of an annotated bibliography, titled "Suggestion for Further Reading," at the end of each chapter, which provides curated recommendations for further academic study.

Thematically, the book is organized in a chronological order that also functions thematically, charting the evolving paradigms of literary studies. Bertens begins by examining the humanistic essentialism of early literary criticism, focusing on the belief that literature serves as a repository of moral instruction. He traces the legacy of Matthew Arnold and the academic professionalization of literature led by figures like T.S. Eliot, I.A. Richards, and F.R. Leavis. From this foundation, it progresses into the text-oriented approaches of *Practical Criticism* and American New Criticism, which shifted the focus toward a micro-level analysis of the text. Bertens discusses how New Critics emphasized paradox, irony, ambiguity, and internal coherence as key markers of literature. He explains that the new critics excluded external factors from their analysis to maintain scholarly objectivity. He details how W.K. Wimsatt and Monroe Beardsley warned against the intentional fallacy, arguing that allowing intentions that are not in some way present in the poem to influence our reading leads to skewed interpretations. They simultaneously established the affective fallacy, warning against interpretations that are unduly influenced by the reader's emotional response to a poem. This focus on form highlights the early twentieth century's pursuit of an objective critical methodology.

Moving chronologically, Bertens navigates the transition from Anglo-American New Criticism to Continental European theories, focusing on Formalism and Structuralism. He explains how Russian Formalists like Victor Shklovsky introduced the concept of

defamiliarization, arguing that literature's function is to make the familiar world seem strange through linguistic devices. Bertens breaks down the distinction between *fabula* (the chronological story) and *syuzhet* or *sjuzhet* (the narrative presentation), demonstrating how form manipulates perception. This discussion bridges into French Structuralism, rooted in the linguistics of Ferdinand de Saussure. Bertens clarifies Saussure's concepts of the arbitrary sign, the signifier, and the signified. He explores how thinkers like Claude Lévi-Strauss applied these models to anthropological phenomena, giving rise to semiotics and narratology. Roland Barthes's dissection of modern myths is presented as an example of structuralism in action. Furthermore, Bertens provides an overview of narratology, developed by figures such as Vladimir Propp, A.J. Greimas, and Gérard Genette. By dissecting narrative mechanics, Bertens demonstrates how structuralism sought to establish a grammar of storytelling. A notable aspect of these middle chapters is the effort to make abstract structuralist concepts comprehensible without oversimplifying the source material.

The book then shifts to the political, social, and identity-based criticism that emerged in the 1970s and 1980s. Bertens provides an overview of Marxist literary theory, exploring how the socio-economic base conditions the cultural superstructure. He details that evolution from traditional Marxist reflection theory — championed by George Lukacs — to the understandings of Louis Althusser's ideological state apparatuses and Antonio Gramsci's concept of hegemony. Through these concepts, Bertens outlines how cultural materialists read texts to expose ideological fault lines. Parallel to this, Bertens explores Feminist criticism, tracing its trajectory from early analyses of patriarchal representations of woman (such as the works of Kate Millet, Sandra Gilbert, and Susan Gubar) to the intersections of gender, class, and race. He underscores how feminism addressed the culturally constructed nature of gender roles and disrupted the male-dominated literary canon.

This leads into discussion of African American literary studies and Postcolonial theory, where theorists like Franz Fanon, Edward Said, and Homi Bhabha deconstruct Eurocentric narratives. Bertens outlines the transition from *négritude* to understandings of diasporic identities, double consciousness, and cultural hybridity. He notes the contributions of critics like Henry Louis Gates Jr., who theorized the strategy of signifying within the Black literary tradition. Bertens highlights the overlaps and underlying tensions between these various politic readings, showing that literature functions as an active political arena.

In its final chapters, the book addresses Poststructuralism, Ecocriticism, Animal Studies, and Posthumanism. Bertens guides the reader through the theories of Jacques Derrida and Michel Foucault. He explains how Derrida's deconstruction addresses the play of *différance*, rendering language ambiguous. Similarly, Foucault's analyses of discursive formations reveal the operations of power and knowledge. Bertens also dedicates space to Queer Theory, noting Judith Butler's arguments regarding the performativity of gender. Exploring contemporary applications, Bertens discusses how ecocriticism addresses the material realities of the Anthropocene and environmental issues. He engages with Donna Haraway's concepts to show how posthumanism and animal studies question traditional boundaries between human, animal, and machine. This thematic progression presents literary theory as an ongoing historical conversation where new ideas react to and revise older ones.

Within the field of literary studies, *Literary Theory: The Basics* occupies a stable position as a foundational introductory text. The landscape of theoretical primers features established works such as Peter Barry's *Beginning Theory* and Terry Eagleton's *Literary Theory: An Introduction*. However, Bertens's volume distinguishes itself through a generally balanced, non-polemic tone. While Eagleton's introduction is driven by specific Marxist

framework, Bertens aims for a scholarly neutrality that allows readers to evaluate the individual merits and limitations of various theoretical schools. The book meets its goal of demystifying theory, operating as a bridge that offers more engagement than superficial summaries while remaining more accessible than primary source texts. It presents theory not as a rigid dogma, but as a toolbox intended for application to cultural and literary artifacts. Bertens's theoretical scaffolding serves not only as a retrospective of historical debates but also establishes an analytical foundation applicable to exploring contemporary and unconventional literary forms. For instance, the insights derived from his chapters on poststructuralism, cultural materialism, and narratology provide useful frameworks for readers analysing boundary-defying genres such as theory-fiction, autotheory, and autofiction. These hybrid texts require the type of analytical decoding outlined by Bertens. Furthermore, the book's exploration of gender performativity, sexuality, and queer studies offer relevant critical lenses for dissecting emergent phenomenon like slash fanfiction. While such topics fall outside the traditional academic canon, they remain sites of cultural negotiation that benefit from theoretical investigation. By equipping readers with these foundational tools, the text supports the exploration of cultural aspects outside traditional parameters.

Ultimately, *Literary Theory: The Basics* is a functional and reliable guide for those navigating modern literary studies. Its target audience includes undergraduate and graduate students encountering critical theory, as well as readers seeking a refresher on theoretical paradigms. Bertens notes that reading is not neutral activity, and theory provides tools to analyse the ideologies embedded within fiction. The book's structure, annotated reading lists, and clear prose help explain concepts like logocentrism, heteroglossia, and intertextuality without excessive complication. By demonstrating that theory can enhance the reading of literature through an awareness of underlying meanings and power dynamics, this book serves as a practical resource for developing reading skills.

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BOOK REVIEW

Between Anchoring and Elsewhere: Aspects of Place in Northern Irish Poetry

Péter Dolmányos, Eger, Budapest, Paris: L'Harmattan Open Access, 2025, 150 pp.

From the middle of the twentieth century onwards, the issue of space gradually became a central topic within the humanities. One of the earliest examples of this preoccupation was Michel Foucault's seminal essay "Of Other Spaces" published in 1967. In this essay, Foucault argued that the humanities had entered an "epoch of space" and predicted that in subsequent decades space would "form the horizon of our concerns, our theory, our systems" (1986 [1967]: 22). It is clear today that these predictions were accurate. Fuelled by accelerating globalisation and the resulting hypermobility, by increasingly pressing concerns over borders and migration, and by the growing importance of virtual spaces, our fascination with space and place is now deeper than ever. While earlier spatiality scholars tended to focus on urban places, the countryside has recently started to take centre stage. Today, scholars are beginning to rethink the nostalgic pastoral ideals associated with rural areas in light of contemporary realities, especially globalisation, capitalism, and the climate crisis (see for example Gifford 2014 or Shucksmith 2018).

In literary studies, the spatial turn is equally evident and interest in literary representations of space shows no signs of waning. A number of scholars have noted that contemporary literature is characterised by a return to materialism (Tew and Mengham, 2006; Turner, 2013; Walezak, 2022; etc.) and frequently engages thematically with ecology and the environment. Naturally, when studying texts rooted in the physical world, space and place become essential analytical categories. Péter Dolmányos's most recent monograph *Between Anchoring and Elsewhere: Aspects of Place in Northern Irish Poetry* is part of this debate. Dolmányos explicitly situates his research within this context in the first chapter of the book, where he emphasises the importance of engaging with the concept of space in literature in general, and in Northern Irish literature in particular. Drawing on the work of theorists of spatiality, such as Henri Lefebvre or Edward Soja, as well as postcolonial scholars, including Edward Said, Dolmányos adopts Elmer Kennedy-Andrews's argument that "[p]lace is increasingly viewed as the product of global, interconnecting flows of peoples, cultures and meanings – of routes rather than roots" (Kennedy-Andrews qtd. in Dolmányos 2025: 19), problematising the view of place as stable or fixed. Instead, Dolmányos understands place as ever-changing, shaped by its relationship to other places, as well as by time, distance, and perspective.

In the remaining seven chapters of the monograph, Dolmányos attempts to uncover the meaning of place in the works of four Northern Irish poets: Seamus Heaney, Michael Longley, Derek Mahon, and John Montague. Throughout the volume Dolmányos successfully argues that each of these four poets portrays the locations in which their verses are set as ambiguous and unstable. Forces ranging from the weather and the sea to the slipperiness of memory cause the places of these poems to change their nature, as well as their meaning. In Chapter 2 Dolmányos outlines Seamus Heaney's poetics of place, noting that Heaney's understanding of place is always twofold: lived and learned, and these "two ways of knowing a place" (30) exist in "a dynamic relationship, challenging and in turn reinforcing each other" (43), a relationship

that Heaney himself described as a “marriage between the geographical country and the country of the mind” (qtd in Dolmányos 2025: 31). In Chapter 3 Dolmányos shifts his focus to the poetry of Derek Mahon. He argues that the geography depicted in Mahon’s work is fundamentally ambiguous, since Mahon is “not a practitioner of minutely executed detailed descriptions of locations” (45). Instead, the poet assigns a major role to the perspective of the lyrical subject. This allows him to construct places that are not stable but created anew with every change in the perspective of the speaker. Chapter 4 presents a discussion of Michael Longley’s concept of home. Dolmányos argues that Longley represents the home as “a non-exclusive category which can thus be associated with more locations” (63). The two places described as home in Longley’s work are Belfast, the city of his childhood, and his country residence. Yet, although the “city of Belfast remains an essentially figurative, predominantly metonymic presence in Longley’s poems” (66), it is through the juxtaposition between the two homes that the central significance of the County Mayo home from home is articulated.

In Chapters 5 and 6 Dolmányos reads the poetry of John Montague and Seamus Heaney, respectively, through a pastoral lens. He concludes that although both poets explicitly engage with the tradition, they ultimately find the pastoral mode inadequate. Montague rejects the idealisation of the pastoral. Instead, he depicts landscapes “in their tangible and often unattractive details” (79) and critiques the pastoral tradition “as one that fails to offer a credible and acceptable representation of proper lived experience” (89). This is also the case in Heaney’s poetry, where “the anti-pastoral is a constant feature” (108). However, instead of a wholesale rejection of the pastoral, Heaney “incorporates the tradition as well as its critique, pointing towards the post-pastoral” (ibid.) as defined by Terry Gifford. In Chapter 7 we return to Derek Mahon. This time Dolmányos shifts his focus to the concept of elsewhere, which is a recurring motif in Mahon’s work. Dolmányos argues that Mahon employs the motif “to facilitate more general reflections on experience by their difference from the familiar environment”, allowing him to “readjust the speaker’s relation to that environment” (126). The final chapter of the monograph returns to the poetry of John Montague, focusing on the motif of borders and border crossing in his 1984 collection *The Dead Kingdom*. Considering the island’s turbulent history, it comes as no surprise that borders feature prominently in the Irish poetic imagination. In the analysed collection, the motif of border crossing is explored on multiple levels: as a literal crossing of a physical border, but also as crossing the border between past and present, and between life and death. Dolmányos concludes that the poems in the collection “demonstrate the speaker’s awareness of the entanglement of the personal and the communal, with the latter inescapably bearing upon the former” (132).

Overall, *Between Anchoring and Elsewhere: Aspects of Place in Northern Irish Poetry* offers a truly in-depth examination of the role and significance of place in the work of the four poets. Each chapter provides a detailed and nuanced discussion of a very specific aspect of the representation of places, locations, and landscapes across the four authors’ poetic works, supplemented by insightful close reading sections that help illustrate the more general or theoretical claims. Yet while the book contains a lot of fascinating content, the language and structure of the text might present some challenges for readers. Dolmányos’s dense prose and highly complex sentences occasionally make it difficult to identify the core ideas. Moreover, although individually the chapters are carefully crafted, and each is methodical in presenting its central argument, the connections between them are not always made explicit beyond their shared thematic focus. The lack of both an introduction and a conclusion limits the space the author has to formulate his overall aims and hypotheses or to draw final connections between the ideas presented in the individual chapters. While some of these connections may be inferred

by the reader, they are seldom foregrounded within the individual chapters themselves. Because of this, the book may strike some readers as a collection of essays rather than a monograph advancing a single argument.

Despite these reservations, I believe Dolmányos's book makes a valuable contribution to ongoing discussions of space and spatiality in literature. Given its highly specialised subject matter and demanding style, it will find its audience mostly among literary scholars focusing on spatiality, contemporary poetry, or Irish literature.

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BOOK REVIEW

Cesty k literatuře: Podněty pro literární vzdělávání [Paths to Literature: Inspirations for Literary Education]

Tomáš Jajtner: Nakladatelství Jihočeské university v Českých Budějovicích, 2025, 229 pp.

Teachers must be convinced that they stand in a position of great dignity, entrusted with a noble calling, surpassed by none in importance beneath the sun.

John Amos Comenius

The quotation by Comenius with which Tomáš Jajtner concludes his essay collection *Cesty k literatuře: Podněty pro literární vzdělávání* [*Paths to Literature: Inspirations for Literary Education*] might raise an ironic or even bitter smile on the lips of many for whom the teaching profession has long since lost its aura of nobility or dignity. Likewise, the author's attempt to defend the importance of the literary text in the age of digitalization may also appear somewhat ironic given a contemporary context in which the dominance of images over the written word is seemingly fostering an entirely new means of perception. This mood seems even more pressing with the rise of AI and its suggestion that humans are no longer the only entity capable of producing artistic representations of the world.

Nonetheless, Jajtner's essays can offer solace for those who share his view that the function of the literary text is now more important than ever before, while also reminding readers that the aim of an education in the humanities is to nurture an "autonomous being who is not educated solely for the economic and political system of the state, but in the spirit of the humanistic ideal of education, i.e. as a free personality who thinks independently, and precisely for that reason will have a motive to pursue lifelong learning" (Jajtner 2025: 33, translated from the Czech original).

Within this specific conception of education, literature is seen not only as a means of cultural communication but also as an irreplaceable source for philosophical, aesthetic and ethical understandings of the world. Whether we perceive literature primarily as a repository of traditions and timeless values that develops a reader's cognitive grasp of reality through the lens of aesthetics, or as a form of sharing subjective experiences that deepen the reader's capacity for empathetic interaction within the human community and with the world itself, the literary text remains indispensable in shaping the positive development of subsequent generations of pupils and students. From this perspective, the role of the enlightened, inspired and passionate teacher of literature stands as a vital component of the contemporary educational system and its emphasis on linking the development of critical thinking with aesthetic and ethical education.

Through thirteen chapters, Tomáš Jajtner's book offers encouragement and inspiration to those who aspire to such a role by exploring the literary text and its pedagogical applications from a variety of perspectives. In the sections devoted to lyric poetry, prose and drama, Jajtner explores how specific features and challenges of each of these literary genres combine to offer a holistic reflection of life, but he also places an emphasis on the different aspects of teaching literature, including ethical-philosophical, psychological, aesthetic and linguistic considerations. The essays also proffer various proposals, recommendations and suggestions on how to integrate different perspectives on literary texts in the classroom and how to combine

them with a clear articulation of the role of the artistic narrative in the development of the human personality: “If the goal of education is the aforementioned autonomous being, who does not need to rely solely on authorities but is capable of independently structuring the world, then the ability to understand the meaning of stories and to gain meaningful insight into the workings of language is absolutely essential and indispensable” (Jajtner 2025: 82, translated from the Czech original).

Jajtner should also be commended for his willingness to confront the issue of the “literary canon” in our “post-canonical” age. Although he fully reflects upon and accepts contemporary concerns over traditional approaches to teaching literature through the presentation of an established set of canonical works, he does not exclude the concept of the canon from literary discourse, seeing it instead as a term that draws attention to enduring human values and existential questions. It is precisely the historicizing view of literature, shaped through a focus on selected works of the literary tradition, that clarifies the timelessness of certain values and questions and enables readers to perceive their everyday existence within the broader context of human experience. Jajtner also addresses other challenges involved in teaching literature in the postmodern age, noting, for example, the usefulness of film adaptations of literary works while maintaining that the literary text cannot be fully replaced because of its unique role in shaping the reader’s imagination.

The chapter devoted to teaching literature in the age of the internet and new media is a welcome part of the collection, since these fields perhaps represent the greatest challenge for teachers today, and not only in the subject of literature. Jajtner recommends an approach of “pedagogical realism,” which rejects the demonization of the digital world in favour of the integration of innovative literary forms, such as text-message poetry, into the literary curriculum. At the same time, he stresses that modern literary education must encompass internet communication and its various forms in order to bridge the gap between the media environment in which students are now immersed and their experience within the more traditional environment of the classroom. Jajtner also offers a range of teaching recommendations which will be useful for new teachers setting out on their careers. Over the course of the collection, he stresses the importance of the experiential model of teaching literature, as well as how insights derived from literary interpretation — understood as the “uncovering of the artistic code of communication” — can be transformed in the classroom into a didactic interpretation of the literary text aimed at the “development of the student’s creative communicative abilities” (Jajtner 2025: 203, translated from the Czech original).

Overall, Tomáš Jajtner’s collection of essays is an engaging and enriching work that showcases his considerable erudition and knowledge of the topic while presenting readers with complex interdisciplinary perspectives on the role of the literary text in humanities education. Jajtner argues convincingly for the importance of literary education in shaping the development of autonomous individuals capable of effective coexistence both within the human community and with the world itself.

On the other hand, the breadth and scope of the recommendations offered to literature teachers throughout the book suggest that the collection should be thought of primarily as a kind of reservoir of ideal approaches to the teaching of literature, with teachers being encouraged to draw upon and select those that they can implement in their everyday practice; any attempt to utilize all of the suggestions, inspirations and recommendations presented in the book would amount to a Herculean task. In contrast, however, a greater reflection on the practical realities of working with students in the classroom — for instance, through various practical exercises and specific examples demonstrating how to implement the theoretical

recommendations from the individual chapters — would certainly be appreciated, especially by novice teachers. Practical examples of this nature would arguably be more useful than the series of reflective questions which Jajtner appends to each chapter. It is also somewhat regrettable that the text has been published in Czech, thereby limiting its reach to Czech and Slovak audiences. The collection would undoubtedly be of value to an international readership given the fact that the crisis of humanities and literary education is a global issue. Within this wider discourse, Jajtner's book offers a welcome balance between a respect for the traditional function of literature within the context of humanistic education and the more modern approaches to its teaching that reflect the state of society in the twenty-first century.

We can only hope that Jajtner's work will contribute to the understanding that, in order for teachers to regain a highly dignified position in society, they must fully identify with Comenius's idea that their vocation is truly a noble calling — regardless of the era or conditions under which it is carried out.

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